

Synthesis of [Leu⁵]enkephalin using Fmoc-Amino Acid Chlorides/KOAt

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The coupling of Fmoc-amino acid chlorides can be mediated by the potassium salt of 1-hydroxy-7-azabenzotriazole. Thus the synthesis of [Leu⁵]enkephalin has been accomplished in good yield and purity.

9-Fluorenylmethoxycarbonylamino acid chlorides^{1,2}, demonstrated to be optically pure, rapid, efficient, shelf-stable, less expensive reagents, were used for the coupling of amino acids in presence of either an inorganic base requiring a biphasic medium or a mixture of an equimolar quantity of tertiary organic base. Sivanandaiah *et al.*³ employed potassium salt of 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (KOBt) in place of 1 : 1 mixture of tertiary base and HOBT. The advantages of 1-hydroxy-7-azabenzotriazole (HOAt) in place of HOBT in peptide synthesis was demonstrated by Carpino *et al.*⁴. It is an efficient additive resulting in rapid coupling processes. The present paper demonstrates that acylations using Fmoc-amino acid chlorides can be carried out in the presence of potassium salt of HOAt (KOAt, Scheme 1). The coupling reaction is complete within 10–15 min. The physical constants of several dipeptides made are given in Table 1. As the reaction is carried out without any organic base, the formation of the corresponding oxazolone leading to racemization is avoided (Scheme 2). The pmr spectra of Carpinos model⁵ diastereomeric dipeptides (Fmoc-Phg-Ala-OMe) [δ 3.58 (s, OCH₃)] and Fmoc-D-Phg-Ala-OMe [δ 3.64 (s, OCH₃)] synthesized by this method clearly showed that coupling reactions are free from racemization.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of a dipeptide (Y = carboxyl protecting group).

Scheme 2

Employing this methodology, namely, Fmoc-amino acid chlorides/KOAt, the solution phase synthesis of the opioid pentapeptide [Leu⁵]enkephalin (Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu) was achieved. The yield as well as purity of the final peptide is satisfactory. The synthetic peptide exhibited biological activity⁶ (guinea pig ileum assay, analgesic effect and antidiarrhoeal activity) similar to that of the natural molecule.

TABLE 1—PROTECTED DIPEPTIDE ESTERS*

Sl. no.	Peptide** / (Mol. formula)	M.p. (°C)	R _f value		[α] _D ²⁵
			R _f A	R _f B	
1.	Fmoc-Ile-Pro-OMe (C ₂₇ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₅)	65–66 (69)	0.63	0.74	–66° (c 0.4, CH ₂ Cl ₂)
2.	Fmoc-Aib-Ala-OMe (C ₂₉ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₅)	121–22 (71)	0.60	0.75	–19.3° (c 1, CH ₂ Cl ₂)
3.	Fmoc-Sar-Ile-OBzl (C ₃₁ H ₃₄ N ₂ O ₅)	Oil (62)	0.52	0.72	–52.6° (c 1, CH ₂ (Cl) ₂)
4.	Fmoc-MeLeu-Ala-OBzl (C ₃₂ H ₃₆ N ₂ O ₅)	114–16 (76)	0.63	0.72	–62.5 (c 1, CHCl ₃)
5.	Fmoc-Ile-Gly-OEt (C ₂₅ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₅)	111–13 (80)	0.64	0.72	–32° (c 0.5, DMF)
6.	Fmoc-Met-Val-OMe (C ₂₆ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₅ S)	90–92 (71)	0.63	0.73	–12° (c 1, EtOAc)

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

**Abbreviations used are in accordance with the recommendations of the IUPAC-IUB Commission on Biochemical Nomenclature (*Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1974, 40, 314); Aib = α -aminoisobutyric acid, Sar = sarcosine, MeLeu = *N*-methylleucine, Phg = phenylglycine, DMF = dimethylformamide, EtOAc = ethyl acetate.

Experimental

All amino acids used except Gly were of L-configuration. M.p.s. were determined on a Leitz-Wetzlar apparatus

and are uncorrected. Specific rotations were measured on AA-10 polarimeter (Optical Activity, U.K.). Hplc analysis was carried out on Waters Prep LC 3000 system equipped with a Waters 484 tunable absorbance uv detector and a Millipore data module for recording and quantification. Amino acid analysis was carried out using Pico-Tag column. For elemental analysis, peptides dried over P_2O_5 under vacuum for 24 h were used. Nmr spectra were recorded on a Bruker WH 270-FT spectrometer (270 MHz). Tlc was carried out using pre-coated silica gel plates using solvent systems (A) chloroform-methanol (9 : 1, v/v), (B) chloroform-methanol-acetic acid (40 : 2 : 1, v/v), (C) n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 1, v/v) and (D) n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5, v/v) and the R_f values being designated as R_{fA} , R_{fB} , R_{fC} and R_{fD} respectively. Amino acid derivatives and peptide spots on tlc plates and paper strips were visualized using iodine vapours, ninhydrin and Pauley reagent. Fmoc-Cl, Fmoc-amino acid⁷ and their acid chlorides¹ were prepared by the reported procedures.

Fmoc-Phg-Phe-OMe (1) : A mixture of phenyl alanine methyl ester hydrochloric acid salt (0.43 g, 2 mmol) and KOAt (0.34 g, 2 mmol) was suspended in $CHCl_3$ (10 ml). A mixture of Fmoc-Phg-Cl (0.78 g, 2 mmol) and KOAt (0.34 g, 2 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (10 ml) was then added to it with stirring. The mixture was stirred for 10–15 min at room temperature. The completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc. The reaction mixture was washed twice with 10 ml portions of 5% HCl, 5% Na_2CO_3 , sat. NaCl solution and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the solid was crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -hexane, (0.85 g, 80%), m.p. 193–94° (lit.⁵ 194–94.5°) (Found : C, 73.26; H, 5.92; N, 5.96. $C_{33}H_{30}N_2O_5$ calcd. for : C, 74.15; H, 5.61; N, 5.24%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 22.6^\circ$ (c 0.5, DMF) {lit.⁵ + 22.2° (c 0.5, DMF)}; R_{fA} , 0.73; R_{fB} , 0.69; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.9 (2H, t, $CH_2C_6H_5$), 3.16 (1H, t, $CHCH_2C_6H_5$), 3.64 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.25 (1H, t, $CHCH_2O$), 4.5 (2H, d, CH_2OCO), 5.2 (1H, d, CHC_6H_5), 6.2 (1H, d, NH), 6.95 (1H, d, NH), 7.3–7.9 (18H, m, ArH).

Fmoc-D-Phg-Phe-OMe (2) : A mixture of phenylalanine methyl ester hydrochloride acid salt (0.43 g, 2 mmol) and KOAt (0.34 g, 2 mmol) was suspended in $CHCl_3$ (10 ml) and reacted with Fmoc-D-Phg-Cl (0.78 g, 2 mmol) and KOAt (0.34 g, 2 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (10 ml) following the above procedure. Crystallization of the resulting product from $CHCl_3$ -hexane gave the product (0.83 g, 78%) m.p., 192–93° (lit.⁵ 192–94°) (Found : C, 74.26; H, 5.01; N, 5.91. $C_{33}H_{30}N_2O_5$ calcd. for : C, 74.15; H, 5.61; N, 5.24%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 21.3^\circ$ (c 0.5, DMF) {lit.⁵ - 21.6° (c 0.5, DMF)}; δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.9 (2H, d, $CH_2C_6H_5$), 2.98 (1H, t, $CHCH_2C_6H_5$), 3.73 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.25 (1H, t, $CHCH_2O$), 4.5 (2H, d, CH_2OCO), 5.2 (1H, d, CHC_6H_5), 6.2 (1H, d, NH), 6.95 (1H, d, NH), 7.3–7.9 (18H, m, ArH).

[Leu⁵]jenkephalin :

Fmoc-Phe-Leu-OBzl (3) : A mixture of leucine benzyl ester of *p*-toluene sulfonic acid salt (3.0 g, 7.5 mmol) and KOAt (1.22 g, 7.5 mmol) was suspended in $CHCl_3$ (20 ml)

and condensed with Fmoc-Phe-Cl (3.15 g, 7.5 mmol) and KOAt (1.29 g, 7.5 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ following the procedure employed for the coupling of dipeptide **1**. Crystallization of the resulting product from $CHCl_3$ -hexane gave **3** (3.83 g, 83%), m.p. 156–57° (lit.¹ 154–55°) (Found : C, 75.26; H, 6.59; N, 4.64. $C_{37}H_{38}N_2O_5$ calcd. for : C, 75.20; H, 6.50; N, 4.74%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 23.9^\circ$ (c 1, DMF) {lit.¹ - 24.7° (c 1, DMF)}; R_{fA} , 0.92; R_{fB} , 0.73.

Phe-Leu-OBzl (4) : 4-AMP (18 ml) was added to a solution of **3** (2.65 g, 4.5 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (20 ml) and stirred for ~30 min. Additional 40 ml of $CHCl_3$ was added and the organic phase was washed with phosphate buffer (pH 5.5; prepared using 90 g of $NaH_2PO_4 \cdot H_2O$ and 32.7 g of Na_2HPO_4 in 500 ml of distilled water) and then with sat. NaCl solution. The organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting free peptide was isolated by crystallization of the residue from $CHCl_3$ -ether, (1.48 g, 89%), m.p. 174–76°; R_{fC} , 0.52; R_{fD} , 0.49.

Fmoc-Gly-Phe-Leu-OBzl (5) : The amino free dipeptide benzyl ester (1.1 g, 3 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (10 ml) was reacted with Fmoc-Gly-Cl (0.99 g, 3 mmol) and KOAt (0.52 g, 3 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ to yield **5** (1.63 g, 84%), m.p. 131–32° (lit.¹ 130°) (Found. C, 72.36; H, 6.46; N, 6.40. $C_{39}H_{41}N_3O_6$ calcd. for : C, 72.28; H, 6.39; N, 6.49%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 11.8^\circ$ (c 1, DMF) {lit.¹ - 11.5° (c 1, DMF)}; R_{fA} , 0.89; R_{fC} , 0.54.

Gly-Phe-Leu-Bzl (6) : 4-AMP (10 ml) was added to the solution of peptide **5** (1.62 g, 2.5 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (10 ml) to cleave the Fmoc group to yield **6** (0.85 g, 80%), m.p. 168–70°; R_{fC} , 0.54; R_{fD} , 0.40.

Fmoc-Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu-OBzl (7) : The amino free tripeptide benzyl ester **6** (0.85 g, 2 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (8 ml) was reacted with Fmoc-Gly-Cl (0.63 g, 2 mmol) and KOAt (0.35 g, 2 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ to yield **7** (1.15 g, 82%), m.p. 162–64° (lit.¹ 163–64°); $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 8.8$ (c 1, DMF) [lit.¹ - 8.2° (c 1, DMF)]; R_{fA} , 0.84; R_{fB} , 0.66.

Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu-OBzl (8) : 4-AMP (6 ml) was added to a solution of peptide **7** (1.0 g, 1.5 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (8 ml) to deprotect the amino group to yield **8** (0.58 g, 84%), m.p. 154–56°; R_{fC} , 0.37; R_{fD} , 0.43.

Fmoc-Tyr(Bzl)-Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu-OBzl (9) : The amino free tetrapeptide benzyl ester **8** (0.43 g, 1 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (6 ml) was condensed with Fmoc-Tyr(Bzl)-Cl (0.51 g, 1 mmol) and KOAt (0.17 g, 1 mmol) in $CHCl_3$ (6 ml), and the product was chromatographed over silica gel column using the solvent ethyl acetate-hexane-acetic acid (90 : 10 : 1, v/v). Fractions containing the pure protected pentapeptide were collected and evaporated. The resulting residue was crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -hexane to yield **9** (1.5 g, 80%), m.p. 175–77° (lit.¹ 178°) (Found : C, 71.40; H, 6.43; N, 7.39. $C_{57}H_{60}N_5O_9$ calcd. for : C, 71.35; H, 6.32; N, 7.31%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 17.6^\circ$ (c 1, DMF) {lit.¹ - 16.9° (c 0.9, DMF)}; R_{fA} , 0.83; R_{fB} , 0.59.

Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu (10) : The final deblocking of N^{α} -Fmoc and Bzl groups of the peptide **9** (0.500 g, 0.5

mmol) was removed by catalytic transfer hydrogenation using palladium black (0.7 g), anhydrous methanol (5 ml) and 85% HCOOH (10 ml). The peptide was isolated by filtration and washed with hot methanol. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with ether in order to remove 9-methylfluorene. The peptide was crystallized from methanol-ether. The resulting peptide salt, Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Leu.HCOOH was then stirred with aq. NaHCO₃ (2%, 20 ml) for ~20 min and extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 40 ml). The organic layer was evaporated under reduced pressure to give **10** (0.225 g, 75%), m.p. 163–64° (lit.⁸ 206°) (Found : C, 60.40; H, 6.79; N 12.0. C₂₈H₃₇N₅O₇ calcd. for : C, 60.49; H, 6.73; N, 12.61%); [α]_D²⁵ –22.9° (c 1, DMF) {lit. –23.6° (c 1, DMF)}; R_fC, 0.51; R_fD, 0.78.

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